

A Comparison between Personality & Sport Competitive Anxiety among Basketball Players at Different Levels Achievement

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Introduction

Sport psychology is an interdisciplinary science that drawn on knowledge from many related fields including biomechanics, Physiology, Kinesiology, and Psychology. It involve that the study of how psychological factors affect performance and how participation in sport and exercise affect psychological and physical factors. In addition to instruction and training of psychology skills for performance improve, applied sport psychology may include work with athletes, coaches and parent regarding injury, rehabilitation, communication, team building and career transitions. Sport Psychology is a proficiency that uses psychological knowledge and skills to address optimal performance and well being of athletes, development and social aspects of sports participation, and systemic issue associated with sports setting and organizations.

Objectives

The objective of the study was to compare the personality and sport competitive Anxiety between the National and State Basketball players.

Methodology

For this study male Basketball players were selected. The subject ranging 18-25 years only. For this study National and State Basketball players were selected. For the collection of Data researcher employing a standardized questionnaire. Personality were measure by employing Eysenck personality Inventory and sport competitive Anxiety were measure by employing Martin's sports competitive Anxiety test.

Result

Extrovert Personality trait

Variables	Mean	S.D.	Mean Differences	S.Error	'T' value
National Players	12.2	1.19	0.93	0.46	2.022
State Players	13.13	2.22			

Neuroticism Personality trait

Variables	Mean	S.D.	Mean Differences	S.Error	'T' value
National Players	14	1.94	1.00	0.49	2.04
State Players	13	1.87			

Sport Competitive Anxiety

Variables	Mean	S.D.	Mean Differences	S.Error	'T' value
National Players	18.13	2.16	0.97	0.44	2.20
State Players	17.16	1.17			

Conclusion

While comparing the Personality and Sport competitive Anxiety it was observed that the National Basketball players had shown significantly better in Personality and Sport Competitive Anxiety as compare to State Basketball Players.

References

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